

Contemporary Gospel Ministers and Modern Technologies

Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI, PhD

Department of Religious Studies, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

afolaranmi.adebayo@lcu.edu.ng, +2348055159591,

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8057-137X>

Abstract

Modern technologies continue to transform the ways people are living and interacting with one another in this contemporary time. The contemporary Gospel minister has to avail himself the opportunities of these modern technologies in his Christian ministries. This paper aims at interrogating the nexus between the contemporary gospel minister and the use of modern technologies. The research design that was employed in this study was descriptive research design. A Gospel minister must be someone who is well grounded in the words of God, who is connected with the Holy Spirit, and who is informed about trends in technologies around him. He has to intentionally and systematically start using modern technologies. Some ways of using modern technologies were highlighted. A note of warning was given to the Gospel minister about some limitations and dangers of modern technologies. It is, therefore concluded that Gospel ministers should increasingly leverage modern technologies to enhance their ministries in the modern age while they should beware of the limitations and dangers that come with modern technologies and prayerfully look for ways to curb these limitations and dangers.

Keywords: Christian Ministries, Contemporary Gospel Ministers, Limitations and Dangers of Modern Technologies, Modern Technologies, Starting Modern Technologies Usage in Christian Ministries

Introduction

Technology starts with the beginning of human life on earth. It may be primitive then as people devised various means of technology to meet their daily needs. It goes until the founding of what can be referred to as early modern technologies, such as radio, television, telephone, computer, and the like. Technology has become an integral part of our lives. More people are now embracing the use of technology, especially since the COVID-19 lockdown in 2020. It does not matter whether one is in the remotest village among old people or in the urban setting among the young “net” generation, modern technology is now transforming the ways people live and interact with one another. Against this backdrop, the contemporary gospel minister has to be acquainted with these modern technologies and be ready to intentionally make effective use of them in building their ministries. The thrust of this write-up is to interrogate the nexus between the contemporary gospel minister and the use of modern technologies.

Who is a Gospel Minister

Simply, a Gospel minister is a person who has had a personal encounter with Jesus Christ and decides to serve Him in any way. The person might have had theological or ministerial training, but there are many Gospel ministers today that do not have such training, but they are ministering the Gospel to other people. The most important thing about a Gospel minister is

their personal relationship with God whom they claim they are representing. The Gospel minister must be a Christian exemplary person whose life speaks louder than his ministry or message. Jewell (2004: 159) asserted, “The truly connected Christian leader [or a Gospel minister] who will have an impact in our disconnected world is theologically grounded, spiritually centered, and technologically informed.” This means that a Gospel minister must be well grounded in the knowledge of the word of God, he must be connected with the Holy Spirit, and he must be informed about trends in technologies around him.

What are Modern Technologies

Modern technologies are of many forms. These technologies range from Information and communications technology to web technology, film and video technology, music technology, educational technology, electronics technology, data access technologies, computer network and storage technologies, financial technology, home automation, security technology, sound technology, medical technology, just to mention some few. Specifically, modern technologies that a Gospel minister has to be acquainted of involve the combined use of text, graphics, audio, video, and animation to communicate the Gospel message.

How to Start Using Modern Technologies by Gospel Ministers

This is very simple and at the same time complex. It depends on the kind of modern technologies the Gospel minister, and/or his ministry wants to use in doing it. It also depends on the size of the church/ministry, the nature of the worship, the budget, the involvement of the congregation/people directly involved in the ministry, and a host of other issues. Using modern technologies by a Gospel minister can begin with the Gospel minister himself or a single person – someone who is gifted with organizational abilities and familiar with modern technologies. This person does not have to be a pastor or a full-time staff member of the church. The person does not need to be a media guru with a high-tech background. The person simply needs to be someone who volunteers for the position or the task, or who devotes his time and resources to the use of modern technologies. The person (if not the Gospel minister himself) must be recognized by the Gospel minister and the leadership of his ministry and must assigned the task of bringing order to the ministry.

The Gospel minister (or any other person) who will start (or be saddled with the responsibility of) using modern technologies in a ministry will have to consider these things:

1. *What the Gospel Minister Has:* the person must first consider what he has to work with, what types of modern technologies he or his ministry is using right currently, what resources are available for him or his ministry, how he or his ministry is currently using modern technologies, and availability of equipment, finances, or materials that he or his ministry has currently that fit into the use of modern technologies.
2. *What Gospel Minister Wants:* this has to do with the vision of the Gospel minister, why the Gospel minister wants to use modern technologies, and what the Gospel minister wants to achieve in it because it is important to know where he wants to take the use of modern technologies to in his ministry.
3. *Who the Gospel Minister Needs:* once the Gospel minister knows what he has and where he wants to go, then, he needs to consider the people he will need for the task. The reason is that the use of modern technologies by a Gospel minister should not be a solo operation, no matter how qualified the Gospel minister may be in the usage of modern technologies. Instead, the Gospel minister should recruit willing and skilful

volunteers to fill the various roles. Undoubtedly, recruiting volunteers is one of the most difficult parts of any Gospel minister. So, the Gospel minister can expect to face some challenges at this juncture. The challenge comes both from finding qualified people and finding willing qualified people. It is not about titles. It is about fulfilling important tasks. If no one is qualified, then the Gospel minister has a new task of training people for these positions. If no one is willing, then the Gospel minister has a prayer request (and in the meantime, may need to adjust his expectations for the use of modern technologies).

4. *How the Gospel Minister will Continue:* By the time the Gospel minister has determined his resources, his vision for the future, and the personnel to fill those positions, he is ready to start. From here on, the task does not get any easier. The Gospel minister has to bear some things in mind: technologies always change, challenges will arise, volunteers sometimes quit, equipment regularly fails, it is capital intensive, and there is always the pursuit of improving and growing the use of modern technologies.

Some Key Ways of Using Modern Technologies by Gospel Ministers

Gospel ministers are increasingly using modern technologies to enhance their ministries to reach a wider audience. Here are some key ways modern technologies are being integrated into contemporary Christian ministries:

1. *Sermon Preparation and Delivery:* Gospel ministers can now use modern technologies computers, the Internet, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and the like for sermon preparation, accessing digital resources, and running multimedia content during their ministries. Gospel ministers can deploy modern technological tools like projectors and screens to display song lyrics, sermon notes, and announcements. Gospel ministers can use soft copy Bibles, hymnals, prayer books, and other resources on their devices when ministering.
2. *Multimedia and Communication:* Gospel minister can now utilize modern technology like audio, video, and other media to enhance their ministry experiences. Modern technologies can be used to record parts of meetings and share them online. Gospel ministers can now devote more resources to improve their online presence and reach people through the web.
3. *Evangelism and Outreach:* Christians are embracing ICT as a method of evangelizing the world, fulfilling the Great Commission. So, Gospel ministers can use their online platforms to invite people to visit, read messages, and share the gospel. Modern technological tools such as social media, websites, and streaming platforms provide Gospel ministers with unparalleled reach and accessibility. Gospel ministers can spread their message to a global audience instantly, facilitating evangelism and outreach efforts.
4. *Assistive Technologies:* Gospel ministers can use assistive technologies to preach to people with disabilities in their ministries. Factors like assessing the Gospel minister's knowledge and skills in using ICT, and integrating ICT in preaching to people with disabilities, can help improve their life experience.
5. *Educational Resources:* Modern technologies allow Gospel ministers to access vast sources of theological and biblical resources online. Gospel ministers can study, research, and have more knowledge by effectively using digital libraries, online courses, and databases.

6. *Virtual Ministries*: Gospel ministers can now minister virtually. This was very useful during the COVID-19 crisis when physical gatherings were challenging. Modern technologies enabled Gospel ministers to conduct virtual worship services, prayer meetings, and Bible studies. This ensures continuity of spiritual fellowship and teaching. Gospel ministers can continue to explore more ways of ministering virtually through emerging modern technologies.
7. *Fundraising and Financial Management*: modern technological tools facilitate online giving platforms, crowdfunding for ministry projects, and efficient financial management. This helps Gospel ministers steward resources effectively and transparently.
8. *Community Building*: Online forums, social media groups, and church management software help Gospel ministers foster community among their congregations. They can connect members, coordinate events, and provide pastoral care remotely.
9. *Cultural Engagement*: Through modern technologies, Gospel ministers can engage with contemporary culture more effectively, addressing relevant issues and connecting biblical teachings with everyday life.

Notes of Warning to Gospel Ministers in Using Modern Technologies

Although the contemporary Gospel minister has many opportunities that he can leverage in modern technologies, there are some limitations he has and some dangers he has to beware of in using modern technologies. Many of these limitations and dangers have been highlighted and explained by this writer in his earlier writings. Some of these limitations and dangers are too much reliance on modern technologies, distraction during ministration/worship service, the spread of fake and unverified (or unauthorised) news, abuse of information dissemination through social media, Internet addiction, cyberbullying, Internet fraud or cybercrime, Internet network failure and/or interruption, Internet-illiterate or semi-literate people especially among the older generation, ethical considerations in online interactions, and others.

Conclusion

While the adoption of modern technologies varies across countries, Christian ministries, church groups, and budgets, it is clear that Gospel ministers are increasingly leveraging modern technologies to enhance their ministries in preaching, reaching more people, and fulfilling the Great Commission in the digital age. Balancing technological advancements with the timeless principles of faith and pastoral care remains essential in leveraging modern technological tools for effective ministry in the modern age. However, Gospel ministers must beware of the limitations and dangers that come with modern technologies and prayerfully look for ways to curb these limitations and dangers.

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